

Table 1. Atmospheric temperature, rainfall, and solar radiation during planting time. Nainital, U. P., India, 1985 wet season.

Date	Temperature (°C)		Rainfall (mm)	Sunshine (h/d)
	Maximum	Minimum		
18-24 Jun	40.0	27.7	26.4	6.7
25- 1 Jun	35.1	24.7	48.7	8.8
2- 8 Jul	33.2	25.4	54.4	5.3
9-15 Jul	31.1	24.7	113.0	5.5
16-22 Jul	31.1	24.6	129.9	6.1

243.8 m altitude), we used Beni silty clay loam, fine-silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic Hapludoll with pH 7.5, 1.3% organic C, 0.11% total N, 15.82 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 139.68 kg available K/ha. The region enjoys subhumid subtropical climate with high temperature in May-Jun and heavy rainfall during Jul-Aug (Table 1). Twelve treatment combinations—three

planting dates, two varieties and two N rates—were compared in a randomized block design (Table 2). Varieties Govind and Pant Dhan 4 differed in duration (105 and 130 d).

Significantly higher grain yield was obtained with early planting, high N, and with a short-duration variety under delayed planting. □

Table 2. Grain yield as influenced by planting date, variety, and N rate. Nainital, India, 1985 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Planting date</i> ^a	
25 Jun	5.4
5 Jul	4.8
15 Jul	3.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3
<i>Variety</i>	
Pant Dhan 4	4.2
Govind	5.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
<i>N rate (kg/ha)</i>	
60	4.4
120	5.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2
CV (%)	7.8

^aSeed sowing date in nursery.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of N source and application time on rice

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We studied effects of N sources and application times on Jaya rice grain and straw yields during 1987 kharif (Jun-Sep) at the Cropping Systems Research

Center, Trivandrum (11°N, 77°E, 30 m above mean sea level). We used 3 sources of N at 90 kg N/ha and 4 application times (see table). The basal application was broadcast and incorporated at transplanting time. For topdressing, all sources were broadcast, keeping soil moist and gradually increasing the water level to 2-3 cm. The soil (sandy clay loam, riverine alluvium deposited over laterite soil) contained 0.47% organic C, 120-7.7-58 ppm of

available NPK, and 390 ppm total soil N, with a pH of 5.2 and EC of 0.25 dS/m.

Results show N impact differed with source and with application time. PU gave higher grain (14% moisture) and straw yields when applied in 3 splits (1/3 basal + 1/3 at tillering + 1/3 at panicle initiation). MPCU should be applied entirely as basal or in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering). LGU gave best yields when applied in 2 splits (1/2 basal + 1/2 at tillering) or in 3 splits (1/2 basal + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation). □

Grain and straw yields as influenced by time of application and source^a of urea. Trivandrum, India, Jun-Sep, 1987.

Time ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw yield (t/ha)			
	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean	PU	MPCU	LGU	Mean
Full basal	3.0	3.4	3.0	3.1	4.2	4.1	5.0	4.5
1/2 B + 1/2 T	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4	6.3	5.1	5.6	5.6
1/2 B + 1/4 T + 1/4 PI	2.6	2.6	3.7	3.0	4.4	5.6	5.7	5.2
1/3 B + 1/3 T + 1/3 PI	3.3	2.9	2.7	3.0	4.9	4.6	4.0	4.5
	3.0	3.1	3.3		4.9	4.8	5.1	
	LSD (0.05)				LSD (0.05)			
Time (T)	0.3			Time (T)	0.5			
Source (S)	ns			Source (S)	ns			
T × S	0.5			T × S	0.9			

^aPU = prilled urea, MPCU = Mussoorie phosphate-coated urea, LGU = large granule urea. ^bB = basal, T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation.

Estimation of pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N of floodwater with integrated N management of lowland rice

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Ammonium N and nitrate N in floodwater reflect the N loss that occurs easily in a submerged soil-water system common to lowland rice. The extent of